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CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

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DIGITAL ECONOMY AND INNOVATION AS FACTORS OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Ibragimova Saodat Abdumuminovna

Professor, Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov;

ORCID: 0000-0001-6230-8009

E-mail: saodatib@yandex.com

Sadullayeva Sevara Uchqun qizi

Postgraduate Student, Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov

Abstract: This article examines the priority areas for the development of the digital economy, innovation, and the social sphere in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of global transformations. It analyzes the processes of digitalization of public administration and the modernization of human capital. The article substantiates the need for a comprehensive approach to digital transformation, including institutional reforms, the development of an innovation ecosystem, and ensuring social inclusion.

Key words: digitalization, digital economy, digital transformation, global transformation, innovation, human capital, government reforms, social development, innovation ecosystem.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the digital economy is one of the top priorities of the state, since improving the economic system without the widespread use of information and computer technologies cannot be considered effective. The global transformations of the 21st century are characterized by the rapid digitalization of the economy, the growing role of innovation, artificial intelligence, and platform-based development models. Under these conditions, the digital economy has become a key factor in ensuring the competitiveness of states.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is implementing large-scale reforms aimed at transitioning to a digital economy and an innovation-driven development model. The fundamental strategic documents in this direction are the “Digital Uzbekistan–2030” Strategy and the “Uzbekistan–2030” Strategy, which are focused on modernizing public administration, developing ICT infrastructure, and improving the quality of life of the population [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

An analysis of scientific literature on the digital economy, innovation development, and social transformation shows that this issue is interdisciplinary in nature and is actively explored in both international and domestic research. In global academic thought, the digital economy is considered a new stage in the development of post-industrial society, based on the use of data, digital platforms, and information and communication technologies. Researchers emphasize that digitalization is becoming a key factor in increasing labor productivity, improving the efficiency of public administration, and creating new markets [1].

Particular attention is given to the concepts of Industry 4.0, the platform economy, and data-driven governance. In the works of the World Bank, OECD, and UNDP, digital transformation is interpreted as a comprehensive process that includes the development of infrastructure, human capital, and the institutional environment. It is noted that the success of the digital economy depends not only on the level of technological development, but also on the quality of institutions, the level of digital literacy of the population, and the state’s capacity for adaptive governance [2].

In scientific studies devoted to the countries of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, the digital economy is viewed as a strategic direction for modernizing the national economy. Domestic researchers identify such priority areas as the development of e-government, the digitalization of public services, the formation of the IT industry, and support for the startup ecosystem [3].

Special attention in the literature is paid to the state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The implementation of the “Digital Uzbekistan–2030” and “Uzbekistan–2030” strategies is regarded as a systemic basis for the country’s digital transformation. Studies also emphasize the role of IT Park Uzbekistan as an institutional center for innovation development and IT exports, contributing to the country’s integration into the global digital economy [4].

A separate body of research is devoted to the development of human capital. Scholars note that the insufficient level of digital competencies, the shortage of IT specialists, and the limited innovation culture represent major barriers to digital transformation. In this regard, the need to reform the education system, introduce STEM directions, and develop digital literacy programs is emphasized [5].

The social aspects of digitalization are also widely discussed in the literature. It is noted that digital transformation expands access to education, healthcare services, and public services; however, at the same time, it may increase digital inequality between regions and social groups [6].

Thus, the analysis of the literature shows that despite the significant number of existing studies, the issues of comprehensive interaction between the digital economy, innovation policy, and social development in the context of global transformations remain insufficiently explored, especially in developing countries, including Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs the following research methods: systemic analysis of socio-economic processes; comparative analysis of international experience in digitalization; content analysis of regulatory documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan; and generalization of data obtained from the World Bank, the United Nations, and national development strategies.

The information base of the research consists of government programs, analytical reports, and scientific publications devoted to digital transformation processes.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Development of Digital Infrastructure

Within the framework of the “Digital Uzbekistan–2030” program, active development of digital infrastructure is being carried out. This includes the expansion of broadband internet networks, the implementation of 4G and 5G technologies, the development of data centers and cloud technologies, as well as the strengthening of cybersecurity systems [8].

Digitalization of Public Administration

One of the key areas of reform is the development of e-government. This process includes the operation of the public services portal, my.gov.uz, the implementation of interagency electronic interaction systems, the reduction of administrative barriers, and the enhancement of transparency in public services. The digitalization of public administration contributes to reducing transaction costs and improving the efficiency of the state apparatus [9].

Development of the Innovation Ecosystem

A key institution for innovation development is IT Park Uzbekistan, established in 2019, which provides support for startups and IT companies, tax and customs incentives, promotion of IT exports, and the formation of a technological ecosystem [10]. In addition, technoparks and innovation centers are being established in various regions of the country.

Development of Human Capital

Special attention is given to the development of human capital. Priority measures include the implementation of STEM education, the digitalization of the education system, the establishment of IT academies and online courses, and programs aimed at improving digital literacy among the population. Human capital is regarded as a key factor of sustainable economic growth.

Social Development and Digital Inclusion

Digitalization has a significant impact on the social sphere. Major directions include the development of e-learning systems, the expansion of telemedicine services, the digitalization of social services, and the reduction of digital inequality between regions. These measures contribute to the formation of an inclusive digital society.

Innovation Policy and Strategic Priorities

Within the framework of the “Uzbekistan–2030” strategy, the following priority directions have been identified: the development of artificial intelligence, stimulation of investments in ICT, support for the startup ecosystem, and the development of a green and sustainable economy [7].

General Results of the Study

The results of the study show that Uzbekistan is currently at the stage of active digital transformation. However, several challenges remain, including the shortage of highly qualified IT personnel, regional digital inequality, dependence on imported technologies, and the need to strengthen the research and development base. At the same time, the country demonstrates high potential for the growth of IT exports, the development of the startup sector, and the expansion of international cooperation.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The digital economy in Uzbekistan is becoming a key factor of socio-economic development. The implementation of the “Digital Uzbekistan–2030” and “Uzbekistan–2030” strategies provides a solid foundation for the formation of an innovative, sustainable, and inclusive economy.

Priority areas of development include the expansion of digital infrastructure, the strengthening of the innovation ecosystem, the development of human capital, and the promotion of social inclusion. In particular, the development of digital infrastructure and workforce competencies in the field of the digital economy should become one of the principal drivers of sustainable economic growth.

At the same time, in the context of the growing number of cybercrimes, it is necessary to ensure the resilience, stability, and security of digital infrastructure. Strengthening cybersecurity systems and enhancing institutional capacity in this sphere are essential conditions for sustainable digital transformation.

For the further development of digitalization processes in Uzbekistan, special attention should be paid to the following areas: further improvement of professional skills and competencies of specialists in this field; modernization of training and retraining mechanisms and the creation of a competitive environment in educational centers; increasing internet speed, reducing service costs, and ensuring information security for all enterprises and organizations; establishment of electronic accounting systems in enterprises and institutions; development of software platforms for priority sectors of the economy; and continuous improvement of the electronic public services system.

Thus, the consistent implementation of these measures will contribute to enhancing national competitiveness, improving living standards, and accelerating the country’s integration into the global digital economy.

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